

THE IMPACT OF THE PROBLEM OF PROFESSIONAL ETHICS IN JOURNALISM ON THE PERSONALITY OF A JOURNALIST, THE MEDIA AND THE IMAGE OF JOURNALISM IN THE COUNTRY

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***Abstract.** In the era of globalization, when humanity lives in conditions of information attacks, the issues of information ethics and journalistic ethics are becoming increasingly relevant. Any journalistic material published in the media directly affects the image of journalism in a given country and, of course, directly affects the influence of the country, its position in the outside world and, so to speak, its international image.*

***Keywords:** globalization, stereotype, interview, sensationalism, journalistic ethics.*

So how much time do people spend on the media today? Has a culture of receiving and possessing information formed in society? What is the state of affairs with journalistic ethics in communicating reality to the public?

Young audiences increasingly prefer social media and the Internet to traditional media for information. They believe that only adults watch news programs now. They have a stereotype that news programs are too serious and formal.

The speed of receiving quick information via the Internet is higher than via television. However, the information provided by news programs is more trustworthy. One of the main reasons for this is that in a news program, information is conveyed to the audience through the voice of the presenter. In this process, how the public will perceive the news depends on the presenter.

If the image of a TV journalist is successfully formed, then even the public that is not very interested in news programs will immediately become interested in it. In other words, because of watching your favorite presenter, paying attention to the information he transmits and listening to his words, the news program expands its audience.

TV presenter Dildora Rustamova answers the question "What should a good TV presenter be like?" as follows: "She should have a beautiful appearance, be able to speak correctly, not shy away from work, adhere to the requirements of journalistic ethics and, of course, have her own individual image." Indeed, you can direct the audience's attention by first capturing it.

What qualities, according to good image-makers, should a TV presenter have? Many experts highlight the following qualities: healthy appearance, facial harmony, beautiful hair, proportional figure, white even teeth, pleasant voice, harmonious movements, intelligence and confidence. This sequence is not conditional. In fact, when we turn on the TV, the first thing we pay attention to when we see a presenter is his face, hair, clothes and hands. Even before the level of knowledge, we begin to compare his appearance with his sound. Therefore, managers should pay great attention to the qualities above.

When it comes to the problem of journalistic image, it is obvious that traditionally research practice was based on the doctrine of the "ideologically correct image" of the journalist. This doctrine is based on the idea that "the set of permitted roles is correct in all respects" [1], and today the attitude to this issue has changed dramatically.

In particular, a journalist is not limited in his choice of role and style, but their absence can lead to the creation of contradictory images in some programs, which can cause viewers to feel distrust in some of his television programs and in television in general.

The characteristic features of the image of a journalist, especially a television journalist, can be determined not only on the basis of thoughts that arise when watching one or several programs (this is more correctly called the form of the image, its external features), but also on the basis of our daily experience, our goals, the psychological type of personality (this is defined as the substantive aspects of the image).

The audiovisual image of any person is assessed, in particular clothing, behavior, communication with the audience, pleasantness, style of speech, namely five initially perceived characteristics, but it should be noted that they should not be perceived as the main characteristics that make up the image. A TV journalist may have a number of other internal qualities that viewers may not be aware of, but perceive subconsciously, that is, without realizing and not knowing it, under the influence of their individual (psychological, social) characteristics, such as temperament (level of passion), level of education, social status and others.

The professionalism of a journalist or the veracity of the information conveyed by him is perceived by the audience not directly, but indirectly, that is, based on information about this person, such as his level of importance, facts of his violation of the law or moral standards, etc. In this case, his hidden image becomes obvious. As is known, some characteristics that make up the image do not arise because of direct viewing (listening) to the presentation. They are determined because of collecting knowledge and information about a specific person from other sources, as well as the subjective perception of a person at a psychological (internal) level. Based on all this, a holistic idea of the journalist is formed, that is, his image.

Compliance with professional and ethical standards, as well as legal norms, is the basis of a journalist's work and directly affects the image he or she creates. We fully support the statement of Khurshid Dostmuhammad that "today our country has accumulated significant experience in creating laws related to the sphere of mass media" [2]. In this regard, the awareness of journalists of their professional rights and responsibilities is of particular importance in the direct creation of an image.

The general image of TV journalists, in particular ideas about their ethnicity, professional skills, temperament, etc., is the result of our subjective perception and the influence of secondary information from other sources.

Non-verbal means of communication can serve not only as a means of self-expression for a leader, but also as a sign of unprofessionalism: excessive anxiety or self-doubt can be felt in body posture, eye expression, excessive or, conversely, insufficient gesticulation.

The level of linguistic culture in the media is directly related to the image of a journalist and how the public perceives him. It can be said that issues of journalist ratings and the ethics of the native language are two sides of the same coin [3].

As noted above, the issue of the image of journalists plays an important role in the growing role of the media in society. Because the formation of the image of an Uzbek national journalist

imbued with the mentality, traditions and values of our people, is one of the urgent tasks facing our journalism today. In this regard, it is important to study and comprehensively research the audience that is the consumer of the material created and presented by the journalist.

Since the peace and prosperity of the country are largely in the hands of journalists, it should not be forgotten that the main tasks assigned to representatives of this sphere, which require them to be several steps ahead of reality, include ensuring public peace, strengthening solidarity, and informing people promptly and accurately about the latest news and changes. Based on such requirements, the gradually emerging image of the Uzbek journalist is formed. This is because foreign media workers based on the aspects we have mentioned, often present the information they receive without filtering, making sensationalism and the rapid dissemination of information to the public their main task. [4] Due to differences in age, worldview and consciousness of the audience of readers, listeners and viewers, people interpret reality differently, and as a result, people can become critical, precise, impatient or indifferent. Therefore, the fact is that journalists responsible for raising public awareness first need to become fully mature themselves. From this point of view, if we consider real journalism as an active system of society, then at the center of this system should be such immortal values as spirituality, morality, and education. Our people have carefully preserved these three great values for centuries. The relevance of the issue is to correctly form the image of an Uzbek journalist based on these characteristics.

Since the problem of journalistic ethics in the media affects not only the image of journalism in the country, but also the external reputation of the country, it is advisable to always act within the framework of ethical standards. It is important to always remember that journalists, as representatives of spirituality, are role models and examples for people to follow.

The issue of ethics is an important concept not only for the journalistic profession, but also for the audience consuming the media, that is, for any person. The 21st century can rightly be called the century of information ethics. Because today information is everywhere. It is conveyed to the public not only by professional journalists, but also by amateur journalists, bloggers and ordinary people. From this point of view, it is very important that everyone who interacts with information observe ethical requirements. Because each piece of information presented determines the image of not only an individual or journalist, but also the country's journalism. Therefore, the issue of journalistic ethics in the media is becoming increasingly relevant in shaping the international reputation of the state.

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